

**NEGATIVE FACTORS AND IMPACTS OF THE TECHNOSPHERE
ON HUMANS AND THE ENVIRONMENT**

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Human impact on the environment, according to the laws of physics, causes counteractions of all its components. The human body painlessly endures certain influences as long as they do not exceed the limits of adaptation. Man and environment are constantly in interaction, forming a constantly operating system "man - environment". In the process of evolutionary development of the World, the components of this system were continuously changing [1].

Man improved, the population of the Earth and the level of its urbanization increased, the social structure and the social basis of society changed. The habitat also changed: the territory of the Earth's surface and its bowels, mastered by man, increased; the natural environment experienced the ever-increasing influence of the human community, there appeared artificially created by man domestic, urban and industrial environments.

As a result of the active transformational activity of man, he created a new type of habitat - the technosphere. When creating the technosphere, a person seeks to increase the comfort of living, to provide protection from external natural influences. At the same time, technospheric conditions, along with positive ones, also have a negative impact on humans and the natural environment.

The complex of negative factors associated with the creation and development of the technosphere includes:

- chemical pollution - an increase in the content of harmful chemicals in the air, water, soil, food;
- physical (parametric) pollution - changes in the physical parameters of the environment (increase in temperature, noise level, radiation and electromagnetic background);
- biological pollution - an increase in the content of pathogens, an increase in morbidity, the emergence of new dangerous infections;
- negative social and psychological factors caused by social and informational stress, leading to an increase in psychosomatic diseases, an increase in crime, drug addiction, and suicides.

The negative factor of the technosphere is the ability of any element of the technosphere to cause damage to human health, material and cultural values or the natural environment.

The main negative factors of the technosphere are:

- harmful, hard, strenuous work associated with human activity in a production environment with hazardous and harmful factors (work with chemicals, work with sources of noise, vibration, electromagnetic and ionizing radiation, work in hot shops, work at height, in mines, moving loads manually, working in confined spaces, working in a fixed position, evaluating and processing a large amount of information, etc.).
- pollution of air, water, soil and food by harmful and hazardous chemicals caused by the release of toxic emissions and discharges from enterprises, as well as industrial and domestic waste into the environment [2].
- human exposure to noise, vibration, thermal, electromagnetic and ionizing radiation caused by the operation of industrial facilities and technical systems.
- high risk of death or damage to health as a result of man-made accidents and disasters in transport, energy facilities and industry.

- social tension, conflicts and stresses caused by high density and overcrowding of the population.

According to the World Health Organization, more than 1 billion people, or 15% of the world's population, have some form of disability, 80% of them live in developing countries. However, in Uzbekistan, only 2% of the population are registered as persons with disabilities.

How to explain such a large gap between the international and national prevalence of disability? What factors influence the measurement of disability rates in Uzbekistan and how best to collect statistical data? Reliable disability statistics are essential for the inclusion of persons with disabilities. After all, to learn about their existence and social status, we rely mainly on quantitative data. And if you are not taken into account in official statistics, you become invisible to the state and society.

Energy plays a leading role in environmental pollution. In many countries, its development was achieved by the predominant use of thermal power plants (TPP) that burn coal, fuel oil or natural gas. Emissions from thermal power plants are the most detrimental to the biosphere. (TPP) emissions contain ash, sulfur dioxide SO_2 , carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, heavy metal oxides, and more than 100 toxic and radioactive substances. Transport also makes a great contribution to the pollution of the environment with hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide, and nitrogen oxides.

In the conditions of the technosphere, negative impacts are caused by elements of the technosphere (machines, structures, etc.) and human actions. An analysis of the totality of negative factors currently operating in the technosphere shows that anthropogenic negative impacts have a priority, among which technogenic ones predominate. They were formed as a result of the transformative activity of man and changes in the biospheric processes caused by this activity. Most of the factors are of a direct nature (poisons, noise, vibrations, etc.).

However, in recent years, secondary factors (photochemical smog, acid rain, etc.) have become widespread, arising in the environment as a result of chemical or energy processes of interaction of primary factors with each other or with components of the biosphere [3].

The levels and scale of the impact of negative factors are constantly growing and in a number of regions of the technosphere have reached such values when a person and the natural environment are threatened by the danger of irreversible destructive changes. Under the influence of these negative influences, the world around us and its perception by a person changes, changes occur in the processes of people's activity and rest, pathological changes occur in the human body, etc.

Practice shows that it is impossible to solve the problem of complete elimination of negative impacts in the technosphere. To ensure protection in the conditions of the technosphere, it is only realistic to limit the impact of negative factors to their permissible levels, taking into account their combined (simultaneous) action. Compliance with the maximum permissible levels of exposure is one of the main ways to ensure the safety of human life in the technosphere.

Used literature

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